

**LISTERIA DNA EXTRACTION USING THE KIT QIAGEN DNEASY
BLOOD & TISSU**

ISSUER	REDACTOR(S)	SIGNATORY(S)
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PURPOSE OF THE CHANGES
Creation

Changes are marked in the text by a line in the margin.

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Seuls la version informatique et les exemplaires en diffusion contrôlée font foi.

DANGER OF RÉAGENTS

The following reagents should be handled with care:

Proteinase K		GHS08
Buffer AL Buffer AW1		GHS06
Absolute ethanol		GHS03
		GHS07

For any questions, consult the safety data sheets (SDS) provided by the supplier or manufacturer

1. MATERIALS

- Microbiological safety station
- Microtube centrifuge (5000-20000 rcf)
- Adjustable volume pipettes
- Dry bath 37°C±1°C and 56°C±1°C
- Chemical filtration hood
- DNase Rnase free microtubes

2. CULTURE MEDIA AND REAGENTS

2.1 Culture Media

- Selective culture medium for Listeria ALOA
- Non selective agar nutrient medium for growth of Listeria, for exemple Trypticase Soja with 0.6% yeast extract (TSAYE)
- Non selective nutrient broth for growth of *Lm*, for exemple Brain Heart Infusion (BHI)

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2.2 Reagents

- Kit DNeasy Blood & Tissue (Ref 69504 Qiagen)
 - Proteinase K (Ref 1014023)
 - Buffer AL (Ref 1014594)
 - Buffer AW1 (Ref 1014790)
 - Buffer AW2 (Ref 1014592)
 - Buffer AE (Ref 1014572)

- Lysis Buffer

Reagent	Initial concentration	Volume to be added
Tris-HCL	1 M	2 mL
Sodium EDTA	0.25 M	0.8 mL
TritonX-100	100%	1.2 mL
Lysozyme		2 g
Water milli-Q		96 mL

- RNase Solution (Ref A797C Promega)
- Absolute ethanol (Ref 20821.296 VWR)

3. CULTIVATION OF STRAINS

Each strain to be analyzed is isolated on ALOA agar and then incubated at 37°C±1°C for 24 hours ± 2 hours and an additional 24 hours ± 2 hours if necessary.

A characteristic colony of *Listeria monocytogenes* (blue-green colony surrounded by an opaque halo) is then plated onto nutrient agar (e.g. TSAYE) incubated at 37°C±1°C for 18-24h or until satisfactory development.

A colony is then subcultured in liquid BHI medium of at least 3mL for 16-18h at 37±1°C

4. SAMPLE PREPARATION

Microbiological safety station

1 – Using a pipette, transfer 1mL of each bacterial culture in BHI medium to a 1.5 mL microtube

Centrifuge for **5 min at 5000 rcf**

Discard the supernatant

2 – Add 180 µL of lysis buffer to each pellet

Vortex and incubate for **30 minutes at 37°C±1°C**

3 – Add 25 µL of Proteinase K and homogenise the tubes

Add 4 µL of RNase solution A and vortex

Incubate 2 minutes at room temperature

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4 - Add 200 μ L of buffer AL and vortex

Incubate **30 minutes at 56°C \pm 1°C**

5 - Add 200 μ L off absolute ethanol in each tube. Vortex.

6 – Transfer the entire contents of each tube in a column above the waste tube

Centrifuge **1 minute at 10000 rcf**

Remove the waste tube under each column and transfer it to the top of a new tube

7 – Add 500 μ L of AW1 buffer (make sure that the ethanol has been added to the bottle when first used)

Centrifuge **1 minute at 10000 rcf**

Remove the waste tube under each column and transfer it to the top of a new tube

8 - Add 500 μ L off AW2 buffer (make sure that the ethanol has been added to the bottle when first used)

Centrifuge **3 minutes at 20000 rcf**

Remove the waste tube under each column and transfer it to the top of a new microtube DNase RNase Free

9 - Add 50 μ L of elution buffer AE

Incubate for 1 minute at room temperature then centrifuge **1 minute at 10000 rcf**

Add another 50 μ L of AE buffer

Incubate for 1 minute at room temperature then centrifuge **5 minutes at 10000 rcf**

10 - Remove the columns and reseal the microtubes containing the extracted DNA.

The extracted DNAs can be stored at +5°C +/-3°C if used within 48 hours, or frozen at >-18°C for later use.

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